

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and its Link to a Uniform Distribution and Conservation

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be linked directly to conservation of energy. In fact, one may derive it by arguing that $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and that these are both equivalent equations. Alternatively, one may argue that $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)$ unnormalized, where $e_1+e_2=e_3$, i.e. conservation. If this is in fact the case, then an expansion of $f(e/T)$ in powers of e/T , where T is a parameter with units of energy, for $e/T \ll 1$, must yield conservation of energy for $f(e_1)f(e_2)$. The only way for this to occur is for $f(e/T)$ to be related to a uniform distribution (and also for $df/de = -1/Tf$). The only uniform distribution seems to follow from e/T representing the probability to have $e \leq T$, but one must have at least $e=T$, so one has $1-e/T$ in this limit. One may then find the explicit form of $f(e/T)$ by considering expressions like $f(e/N)$ power $N = f(e)$.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is often obtained by maximizing entropy subject to an average energy constraint. Alternatively, one may use:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4) \text{ and } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad ((1))$$

By taking \ln of the first equation and equating it to $-1/T$ of the second one obtains the unnormalized $\exp(-e_i/T)$ solution. In $((1))$, the two equations are not independent and so \ln of one yields the other.

We have suggested in previous notes that the conservation of energy link in the MB distribution follows from:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3) \text{ where } e_1+e_2=e_3 \quad ((2))$$

In other words, it is inherent in the probability itself. One may use $((2))$, in fact, as a definition of a probability which inherently carries the constraint of conservation. This means that for $e/T \ll 1$, $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ should actually reveal conservation of energy. In other words, $f(e/T)$ should become related to a uniform distribution. The only way for this to occur is to have:

$$f(e/T) = 1-e/T \text{ so that } f(e_1)f(e_2) = 1 - e_1/T - e_2/T \text{ to a linear power in } e \quad ((3))$$

$1-e/T$ is the probability to have e or greater for a uniform probability with a range of T . In other words, e/T is the probability to have e or smaller. Thus, at heart, the MB distribution is linked to a linear (or uniform probability) which is a type of power law (power 1). This seems to be because it must respect conservation of energy.

Obtaining Higher Order Terms

If one uses the linear order expression $1 - e/T$, then one needs to find higher order terms. This may be done in the following way. To find the second order term, one may consider:

$$1 - e/T + b \frac{e^2}{T^2} \quad \text{and use:} \quad f(e/2)f(e/2) = f(e) \quad \text{or}$$

$$\frac{e^2}{4T^2} + .5 b \frac{e^2}{T^2} = b \frac{e^2}{T^2} \quad \text{or} \quad b = \frac{1}{2} \quad ((4))$$

To find the third order term, one may use $f(e/3)f(e/3)f(e/3) = f(e)$ and

$$1 - e/T + \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{T^2} + b \frac{e^3}{T^3} \quad \text{so:}$$

$$B = -1/27 + 3b/27 + \frac{1}{2}(-1)^6 (1/27) \quad ((5))$$

This procedure may be used to calculate various terms until one realizes that $1/n!$ seems to be the coefficient. If this is the case, then $f(ei/T) = \exp(-ei/T)$ which intrinsically ensures conservation of energy. Thus, the idea of $f(ei/T)$ intrinsically ensuring conservation of energy seems to be a main idea, and a link with a uniform distribution only appears in the $ei/T \ll 1$ limit.

MB Distribution Derivative

Another way to consider the matter is use:

$$f(e)f(de) = f(e+de) = f(e) + de \frac{df}{de} \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Thus, } f(de) = 1 - de/T \quad \text{and } \frac{df}{de} = -1/T f(e) \quad ((7))$$

This means that a power series of $f(e)$ in e/T should have weights of $1/n!$ for each term. The derivative of df/dx must have the same value as $f(x)$ in order to ensure conservation in:

$$f(x/2)f(x/2) = f(x) \quad ((8))$$

If this were not the case, then ((8)) would not hold. Thus, energy conservation for a low e/T expansion requires $df/de = -1/T f$.

Comparison with a Quantum Mechanical Free Particle Wavefunction

A quantum mechanical free particle wavefunction is $\exp(ipx)$ (one dimension). We have argued in previous notes that this represents motion around a circle with each $d\theta$ having the same weight, i.e. px is linked to a uniform distribution, but one has mapped to a circle. In this case, it is conservation of momentum which is ensured, i.e.

$$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((6))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is directly linked to conservation of energy, i.e. $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)$ and if one may write $f(e/T)$ as a power series in e , then this implies that in the $e/T \ll 1$ limit only the linear term remains and that this must yield conservation of energy. This, in turn implies that $df/de = -1/T f$. $f(e/T)$ must then be linked to a uniform distribution. If e/T is the probability to have $e < T$ and e is small compared to T , i.e. like de then the distribution is $1-e/T$, i.e. the uniform probability to have at least e .

Thus, we suggest that at the heart of the MB distribution is energy conservation and a uniform distribution.